

Wild rice resistance to brown planthopper (BPH)

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We screened 30 wild rice accessions originating in South and Southeast Asia and South America and received from IRRI for resistance to BPH in the greenhouse, using the standard seedbox screening technique. Ptb 33 and TN1 were used as resistant and susceptible checks.

To break dormancy, seeds were kept at 50°C for 5 d. The lemma and palea were removed by hand and 20 seeds/ accession were sown in 15-cm-long rows in wooden seedboxes.

At 7 d after sowing, the seedlings were thinned to 15/row, infested with 8 to 10 first-instar nymphs/seedling, and covered with mylar film cages. Damage rating was done when 95% of the susceptible check plants were killed.

All 30 wild rice accessions were resistant (see table). Wild rices *O. latifolia*, *O. officinalis*, and *O. punctata* also were found to be resistant to BPH biotypes 1, 2, and 3 at IRRI. □

BPH resistance in wild rices. Coimbatore, India, Greenhouse, 1986.

Species	IRRI acc. no. ^a	Origin
<i>O. latifolia</i>	100165	Guatemala
<i>O. latifolia</i>	100167	Costa Rica
<i>O. latifolia</i>	100168	Costa Rica
<i>O. latifolia</i>	100169	Costa Rica
<i>O. latifolia</i>	100171	Guatemala
<i>O. latifolia</i>	100172	Guatemala
<i>O. latifolia</i>	100895	USA
<i>O. latifolia</i>	100914	Mexico
<i>O. latifolia</i>	100956	India
<i>O. latifolia</i>	100959	Mexico
<i>O. latifolia</i>	100962	Guatemala
<i>O. latifolia</i>	100963	Guatemala
<i>O. latifolia</i>	100964	Guatemala
<i>O. latifolia</i>	100965	Costa Rica
<i>O. latifolia</i>	100966	Panama
<i>O. latifolia</i>	101392	Guatemala
<i>O. officinalis</i>	100179	Japan
<i>O. officinalis</i>	100878	Thailand
<i>O. officinalis</i>	100896	Thailand
<i>O. officinalis</i>	100948	India
<i>O. officinalis</i>	101074	Philippines
<i>O. officinalis</i>	101121	Philippines
<i>O. officinalis</i>	101135	Philippines
<i>O. officinalis</i>	101155	Malaysia
<i>O. officinalis</i>	101166	Philippines
<i>O. australiensis</i>	101144	Australia
<i>O. australiensis</i>	101397	USA
<i>O. punctata</i>	101409	Ghana
<i>O. longistaminata</i>	101200	Nigeria
<i>O. alta</i>	101395	USA
Ptb 33 (resistant check)		India
TN1 (susceptible check)		China

^a All except the susceptible check had a damage rating of 1 by the *Standard evaluation system for rice* scale of 0-9.

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization ADVERSE SOILS TOLERANCE

Varieties tolerant of coastal acid saline soils

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Salt-tolerant rice varieties do not perform satisfactorily when salinity is associated with soil acidity. We screened 108 varieties suitable for coastal acid saline soils (pH 3.2, ECe 2.6-4.5 dS/m) at Nirdeshkhali.

RD15 from Thailand gave the highest grain yield (see table). Local variety SR26-B, IR44, IR8067-41-1E-P1, BW100 from Sri Lanka, B2149b-Pn-26-1-1 from Indonesia, and ITA230

from Nigeria appear highly promising. □

Rice varieties' tolerance for coastal acid saline soils at Nirdeshkhali, India.

Variety	Origin	Yield ^a (t/ha)
BG35-2	Sri Lanka	1.9
BW100	Sri Lanka	2.3
B2149b-Pn-26-1-1	Indonesia	2.3
B58b-Mr-105-2	Indonesia	1.5
IR28222-9-2-2-2-2	IRRI	1.6
IR44	IRRI	2.5
ITA230	Nigeria	2.0
Mahsuri	Malaysia	1.8
SR26-B (local check)	India	2.5
IR8067-41-1E-P1	IRRI	2.2
RD15	Thailand	3.1
IR26 (check)	IRRI	0.5
CD (5%)		0.7

^a Mean of 3 replications.

Effect of saline irrigation water on yield

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We studied the effect of saline irrigation water on grain yield of 27 rice varieties in a randomized block design with 3 replications in 1984 kharif. Soil was clayey with pH 8.4 and EC (1:1) 1.5 dS/m. Seedlings were transplanted at 40 d. Treatments were 1 dS/m, 4 dS/m, and 6 dS/m irrigation water. Each plot received 80